

weather parameters and yield showed a positive relationship between total solar radiation during 5-15 d before 50% heading and a negative relationship between number of rainy days 15-30 d before 50% heading. Yield was predicted by these equations:

$$\text{Jaya: } Y = 11.74^{**}X_1 - 308.02^{**}X_2 - 2175$$

(3.91) (2.16)

$$R = 0.73$$

$$\text{IR8: } Y = 10.36^{**}X_1 - 238.80 X_2 - 1720$$

(3.42) (1.65)

$$R = 0.68$$

**Significant at 1% level
*Significant at 5% level

Where, Y = grain yield (kg/ha),
 X_1 = mean solar radiation 5-15 d before 50% heading in mWh/cm^2 per d, and

X_2 = number of rainy days 15-30 d before 50% heading.

Figures in parentheses are the "t" values of the regression coefficients.

Yield declines were more predominant for crops planted 18 Sep, 3 Oct, and 17 Oct, but yield reductions occurred under adverse weather parameters regardless of planting date. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Isolation of restorers and maintainers for two Chinese male-sterile lines having wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm

M. Rangaswamy, K. Natarajamoorthy, G.A. Palanisamy, and S.R. Sree Rangaswamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India

Pollen from 26 early- and medium-duration rice varieties (8 from IRRI and 18 from India) were crossed with cyto-sterile Zhen Shan 97A and 12 varieties (6 from IRRI and 6 from India) were crossed with cyto-sterile Er-jiu Nan 1A to identify restorers and maintainers of pollen fertility. The two cyto-steriles are of Chinese origin with wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm.

The F_1 hybrids were raised during 1985 rabi in a test cross nursery at Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU. The

Pollen parents classified according to spikelet fertility percentage. TNAU, India.

Cytosterile	Effective restorers >80%	Weak restorers			Weak maintainers			Effective maintainers <5%
		60-80%	40-60%	20-40%	15-20%	10-15%	5-10%	
Zhen Shan 97A	-	-	IR36	IR54 IR56 IR58 IET1722 ASD8 TNAU658 K. Samba	IR40 IR50 IR52 IET4786 A09246 Co41	IR9752 TKM9 BAS370 PTB10 TNAU4372 Co 33 Co 37 Co 39	ADT31 PY2 Co 13 Kanchi	-
Er-jiu-Nan 1A	-	IET6208	IR9698 IET5103	IR19053 IR19058 IR9715 IET13267	IR18599	IR2307 AS19789 IET3630	BPHR5	-

main panicle of each hybrid plant was bagged and spikelet fertility was estimated at harvest. On the basis of spikelet fertility, pollen parents were classified as effective restorers (>80% spikelet fertility); partial or weak restorers (20 to 80% fertility), which is again subdivided into three groups;

weak maintainers (5-20%) and effective maintainers (<5%) (see table).

Stable male-sterile lines MS47A, MS37A, and MS31A are being developed utilizing weak maintainers Co 33, Co 37, and ADT31. A program to identify effective restorers and maintainers is in progress. □

Recurrent selection in rice

T. James, E.P. Guimaraes, Brazilian National Research Center for Rice and Beans, CNPAF/EMBRAPA CP179 74000, Goiania GO, Brazil

To complement conventional breeding systems and to facilitate hybrid breeding programs, CNPAF and IRAT are synthesizing populations with broad genetic bases. The ability

of these populations to produce good varieties through conventional breeding or to provide good female parents with high prospects for cross pollination for the hybrid program will gradually increase through cyclic application of intermating and selection.

To facilitate intermating, a recessive male sterile gene [from IR36 male sterile (MS)] was introduced. Control of recombination and conservation of

the MS gene are assured by harvesting only open-pollinated seeds from male sterile segregants.

Two populations, one for irrigated rice and one for upland rice, are now ready to be used in conventional breeding systems. The rate of natural outcrossing on male sterile plants is sufficient to guarantee renovation of the populations. An average 165 seeds from male sterile plants of irrigated rice and 26 seeds from upland rice

(0.5 × 0.5 m interplant space) were collected.

For the hybrid program, we are

synthesizing one population for irrigated rice and one for upland rice. The long stigma of the wild

allogamous species *Oryza longistaminata* is being introduced in these populations. □

Cytogenic relationship between two cytoplasmic male-sterile lines

S.S. Virmani and R. C. Dolores Dalmacio, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

Cytoplasmic-genetic male sterility (CMS), conditioned by the interaction of nuclear and cytoplasmic factors, is used extensively in hybrid breeding programs for self-pollinated crops. Hybrid varieties grown commercially in China are derived mostly from cytoplasmic sources of wild rice *Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea*, designated as WA (wild rice with aborted anthers). Alternative sources of cytotosterility are needed to protect F₁ hybrids against potential genetic vulnerability to diseases and insects.

We have developed a new CMS (A) line, IR54755A, which has the cytoplasm of land race ARC13829-16 introduced from Assam, India, and the nuclear genotype of elite breeding line IR10179-2-3-1. Another CMS line, IR46828A, was developed in the same nuclear genotype with the WA cytoplasm from Chinese CMS line Zhen Shan 97A. We studied the cytogenic relationship between the two cytotesterile lines developed from the two different cytoplasmic sources.

Each CMS line was crossed with its maintainer and single plant selections of a number of other maintainers,

Pollen fertility behavior of F₁ progenies between CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines. IRRI, 1986 dry season.

Male parent	Female parent											
	IR46828A					IR54755A						
	Plants (no.)	F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class ^a					Plants (no.)	F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				
	CS	S	PS	PF	F		CS	S	PS	PF	F	
IR54755B	19	19	0	0	0	0	48	48	0	0	0	0
IR46828B	49	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
IR46829B	9	7	2	0	0	0	10	10	0	0	0	0
IR46830B	8	8	0	0	0	0	10	10	0	0	0	0
IR36R	9	0	0	0	0	9	8	0	0	0	2	6
IR46R	9	0	0	0	0	9	10	0	0	0	0	10
IR64R	6	0	0	0	0	6	10	4	3	1	2	0
IR9761-19-1R	6	0	0	0	0	6	6	0	0	0	1	5
IR28	9	0	0	0	0	9	9	0	2	0	3	4
IR34	5	2	2	1	0	0	10	9	1	0	0	0
IR43	10	6	4	0	0	0	10	5	3	2	0	0
IR52	8	0	0	0	0	8	10	0	0	0	0	10

^a pollen fertility classes: cs = completely sterile, 0% pollen fertility; s = sterile, 1-10% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 11-30% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 31-60% pollen fertility; F = fertile 61-100% pollen fertility.

restorers, and partial restorers of the WA cytotesterility system. The F₁ population of these crosses was evaluated for pollen fertility using 1% IKI solution.

The maintainers of the two CMS lines (IR54755B and IR46828B) effectively maintained the male sterility in the two cytotesterile lines (see table). However, IR64R, IR9761-19-IR, IR28, IR34, and IR43 showed differential fertility in crosses with the two CMS lines.

These results indicate that the cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility in IR46828A and IR54755A may be different. The maintainers IR46828B and IR54755B, derived from the line IR10179-2-3-1, have genotypes capable of maintaining both cytotesterility systems. The cytogenic differences observed here need to be substantiated by analysis of mitochondrial DNA of the two CMS lines. □

Survival of some F₁ rice hybrids and their parents in saline soil

D. Senadhira and S. S. Virmani, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

Increased vegetative and root vigor are useful traits to use in adapting rice plants to soil and climatic stresses. Usually, F₁ hybrids express these traits. We evaluated 12 F₁ rice hybrids

and their parents for survival in saline soil at IRRI in the 1986 dry season. Although the hybrids' parents are not known to be tolerant of salinity, our objective was to test the usefulness of hybrid vigor under such stresses as soil salinity.

Five-wk-old seedlings grown on wet seedbeds were transplanted at 50 hills/entry in a field where salinity to an EC of 7 dS/m had been induced by

adding common salt. Check varieties were IR28 (salt sensitive) and IR9884-54-3 (salt tolerant). The field salinity level was maintained throughout the experiment. Plant survival was recorded at 6, 12, and 15 wk after transplanting.

Salinity prolonged the growth duration of all varieties tested. Very early parents and hybrids flowered about 100 d after seeding.